

Design of a Maintenance Protocol based on Bipolar Neutrosophic Analysis for Severe Depression

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Abstract. Severe depression has been one of the leading causes of disability worldwide and maintains a high risk of relapses even after successful treatment, especially in medium-sized cities in Latin America. Therefore, this study focused on the design of a clinical maintenance protocol based on Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT), aimed at young adults residing in Ambato, Ecuador, who had previously received Cognitive-Behavioral Therapy (CBT). To this end, a bipolar neutrosophic analysis of depression was conducted to determine the attributes that impact the identified patients and define the design of the proposal. The designed protocol was structured into eight group sessions, with an experiential approach centered on the six core processes of ACT. Evaluation strategies were also proposed to measure processes and outcomes. It was concluded that the protocol seeks to strengthen therapeutic continuity, reduce relapses, and promote sustained emotional well-being in young people with a history of depression.

Keywords: Relapse prevention, Psychological treatment, Mental health, Therapeutic follow-up, Bipolar neutrosophic set.

1 Introduction

Major Depressive Disorder (MDD) in its severe form constitutes one of the most disabling psychiatric conditions, profoundly affecting the emotional, social, and occupational functioning of those who suffer from it. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), more than 280 million people live with depression, and it represents one of the leading causes of disability worldwide [1]. Although effective treatments exist to address the acute phase, such as Cognitive-Behavioral Therapy (CBT), relapse rates remain high, particularly among young people who have experienced severe episodes [2].

This vulnerability intensifies during the transition to adulthood, a stage considered critical from an emotional development perspective, as it coincides with academic pressures, vocational uncertainty, and the search for identity [3]. These factors, as various studies have indicated, increase the risk of emotional dysregulation and psychological fragility.

On the other hand, it is exacerbated by poor therapeutic continuity, insufficient community mental health infrastructure, and the persistent social stigma that weighs on those who have received psychological or psychiatric care [4] [5]. For instance, in the city of Ambato, located in the central region of Ecuador, the availability of post-treatment programs is severely limited, compromising the possibility of sustaining the therapeutic gains achieved during the acute phase.

In response to this situation, the present study begins its analysis from a bipolar neutrosophic representation of depression and its treatments through the use of sets [6]. This approach seeks to identify a subset of young people who have experienced episodes of high emotional intensity and who have received prior treatment with CBT. As well as to design a clinical maintenance protocol based on Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT), aimed at young adults residing in Ambato, Ecuador, who have received prior CBT treatment [7].

Given that it constitutes an interaction between CBT and ACT treatments for this identified subset,

each interacting attribute is analyzed by positively examining the effects on patient health. At the same time, negative elements are assessed, such as low professional experience, patient health coverage, or similar clinical conditions defined within the range. Therefore, the use of bipolar Neutrosophy is proposed for the development and structure of the study.

Finally, the proposed clinical protocol seeks to consolidate the progress achieved during the acute phase, reduce the risk of relapse, and promote sustainable emotional well-being. Additionally, it is proposed as a group intervention adapted to the local psychosocial environment, contributing to stigma reduction and strengthening the therapeutic support network in young adults [5].

2 Preliminaries

2.1 Neutrosophic SuperHyperSoft Sets.

Definition 1 [8]. The *Neutrosophic set* N is characterized by three membership functions, which are the truth-membership function T_A , indeterminacy-membership function I_A , and falsity-membership function F_A , where U is the Universe of Discourse and $\forall x \in U, T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \subseteq]^{-}0, 1^{+}[$, and $^{-}0 \leq \inf T_A(x) + \inf I_A(x) + \inf F_A(x) \leq \sup T_A(x) + \sup I_A(x) + \sup F_A(x) \leq 3^{+}$.

See that according to the definition, $T_A(x), I_A(x)$, and $F_A(x)$ are real standard or non-standard subsets of $]^{-}0, 1^{+}[$ and hence, $T_A(x), I_A(x)$ and $F_A(x)$ can be sub-intervals of $[0, 1]$. $^{-}0$ and 1^{+} belong to the set of hyperreal numbers.

Definition 2. The *Single-Valued Neutrosophic Set (SVNS)* A over U is $A = \{ \langle x, T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle : x \in U \}$, where $T_A: U \rightarrow [0, 1]$, $I_A: U \rightarrow [0, 1]$ and $F_A: U \rightarrow [0, 1]$. $0 \leq T_A(x) + I_A(x) + F_A(x) \leq 3$. A single valued neutrosophic number is denoted by $\tilde{A} = \langle T, I, F \rangle$ for convenience.

Definition 3. Let $\tilde{A}_1 = \langle T_1, I_1, F_1 \rangle$ and $\tilde{A}_2 = \langle T_2, I_2, F_2 \rangle$ be two single-valued neutrosophic numbers. Then, the operations for NNs are defined as below;

$$\lambda \tilde{A} = \langle 1 - (1 - T_1)^\lambda, I_1^\lambda, F_1^\lambda \rangle \tag{1}$$

$$\tilde{A}_1^\lambda = \langle T_1^\lambda, 1 - (1 - I_1^\lambda), 1 - (1 - F_1^\lambda) \rangle \tag{2}$$

$$\tilde{A}_1^\lambda + \tilde{A}_2^\lambda = \langle T_1 + T_2 - T_1 T_2, I_1 I_2, F_1 F_2 \rangle \tag{3}$$

$$\tilde{A}_1^\lambda \cdot \tilde{A}_2^\lambda = \langle T_1 T_2, I_1 I_2 - I_1 I_2, F_1 + F_2 - F_1 F_2 \rangle \tag{4}$$

where $\lambda > 0$.

Definition 4. Let X be a non-empty set. Then, a bipolar-valued fuzzy set, denoted by A_{BF} , is defined as; $A_{BF} = \{ \langle x, \mu_B^+(x), \mu_B^-(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$ where $\mu_B^+(x) \rightarrow [0, 1]$ and $\mu_B^-(x) \rightarrow [0, 1]$. The positive membership degree $\mu_B^+(x)$ denotes the satisfaction degree of an element x to the property corresponding to A_{BF} and the negative membership degree $\mu_B^-(x)$ denotes the satisfaction degree of x to some implicit counter property of A_{BF} .

Definition 5 [9]. Let A bipolar neutrosophic set A in X is defined as an object of the form $A = \{ \langle x, T^+(x), I^+(x), F^+(x), T^-(x), I^-(x), F^-(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$, where $T^+, I^+, F^+: X \rightarrow [1, 0]$ and $T^-, I^-, F^-: X \rightarrow [-1, 0]$. The positive membership degree $T^+(x), I^+(x), F^+(x)$ denotes the truth membership, indeterminate membership and false membership of an element $x \in X$ corresponding to a bipolar neutrosophic set A and the negative membership degree $T^-(x), I^-(x), F^-(x)$ denotes the truth membership, indeterminate membership and false membership of an element $x \in X$ to some implicit counter-property corresponding to a bipolar neutrosophic set A .

Definition 6 [10]. Let $\tilde{a}_1 = \langle T_1^+(x), I_1^+(x), F_1^+(x), T_1^-(x), I_1^-(x), F_1^-(x) \rangle$ and $\tilde{a}_2 = \langle T_2^+(x), I_2^+(x), F_2^+(x), T_2^-(x), I_2^-(x), F_2^-(x) \rangle$ be two bipolar neutrosophic number. Then the operations for NNs are defined as below;

$$\lambda \tilde{a}_1 = \langle 1 - (1 - T_1^+)^\lambda, (I_1^+)^\lambda, (F_1^+)^\lambda, -(-T_1^-)^\lambda, -(-I_1^-)^\lambda, -\left(1 - (1 - (-F_1^-))^\lambda\right) \rangle \tag{5}$$

$$\tilde{a}_1^\lambda = \langle (T_1^+)^{\lambda}, 1 - (1 - I_1^+)^{\lambda}, 1 - (1 - F_1^+)^{\lambda}, -(1 - T_1^-)^{\lambda}, -(-I_1^-)^{\lambda}, -(-F_1^-)^{\lambda} \rangle \quad (6)$$

$$\tilde{a}_1 + \tilde{a}_2 = \langle T_1^+ + T_2^+ - T_1^+T_2^+, I_1^+I_2^+, F_1^+F_2^+, -T_1^-T_2^-, -(-I_1^- - I_2^- - I_1^-I_2^-), -(-F_1^- - F_2^- - F_1^-F_2^-) \rangle \quad (7)$$

$$\tilde{a}_1 \cdot \tilde{a}_2 = \langle T_1^+T_2^+, I_1^+ + I_2^+ - I_1^-I_2^-, F_1^+ + F_2^+ - F_1^-F_2^-, -(-T_1^- - T_2^- - T_1^-T_2^-), -I_1^-I_2^-, -F_1^-F_2^- \rangle \quad (8)$$

Where $\lambda > 0$.

Definition 7. Let $\tilde{a}_1 = \langle T_1^+, I_1^+, F_1^+, T_1^-, I_1^-, F_1^- \rangle$ be a bipolar neutrosophic number. Then, the score function $l(\tilde{a}_1)$, accuracy function $a(\tilde{a}_1)$ and certainty function $c(\tilde{a}_1)$ of a bipolar neutrosophic number are defined as follows:

$$i. \quad \tilde{l}(\tilde{a}_1) = \frac{(T_1^+ + 1 - I_1^+ + 1 - F_1^+ + 1 + T_1^- - I_1^- - F_1^-)}{6} \quad (9)$$

$$ii. \quad \tilde{a}(\tilde{a}_1) = T_1^+ - F_1^+ + T_1^- - F_1^- \quad (10)$$

$$iii. \quad \tilde{c}(\tilde{a}_1) = T_1^+ - F_1^- \quad (11)$$

3 Results

3.1 Bipolar neutrosophic analysis: Depression and its functional implications.

Depression constitutes a mental disorder fundamentally characterized by sadness and discouragement. It is also associated with physical and cognitive alterations, affecting the patient's functional development, as well as social relationships and language. In fact, different types of depression exist, each with its own characteristics and duration. The most common are major depressive disorder and persistent depressive disorder (also called dysthymia). Additionally, there are other types such as seasonal affective disorder, perinatal depression, and depression with psychotic features. Therefore, for the development of this study, it is proposed to identify each of these elements in the following attributes by sets:

- s_n : Set of symptom manifestations according to intensity, duration, number of symptoms, and level of functional interference.
- d_n : Set of depression subtypes (manifestation of subsets in different depression subtypes according to s_n)
- t_n : Set of treatments and their structures (t_1 : psychotherapy, t_2 : pharmacotherapy, t_3 : electroconvulsive).

Consequently, each of these attributes responds to the following function $f(\{s_n\}) \rightarrow d_n$ and $f(\{d_n\}) \rightarrow t_n$, according to the image of the selected set or subset. Given that the manifestations of s_n , d_n and t_n imply elements with bipolar characteristics, it becomes necessary to use bipolar Neutrosophy to determine the positive and negative effects. For example, in one or several subsets belonging to s_n implies in the function multiple neutrosophic structures that are defined according to the type of complexity and structure:

- $\{s_1\}, \{s_2\}, \{s_n\}, \{\{s_1\}, \{s_2\}\}, \{\{s_1\}, \{s_n\}\}, \{\{s_2\}, \{s_n\}\}, \{\{s_n\}, \{s_n\}\}$

To illustrate, in the structures of s_n several symptoms with different degrees of complexity can co-exist; however, these depend on the clinical evaluation given by the specialist. In fact, each expert or professional who diagnoses the depression subtype must determine how true the diagnosis is, indeterminate in cases where the present symptoms do not show the degree of manifestation required according to the Beck Depression Inventory-II (BDI-II) or through the defined DSM-5 criteria. They must also determine the level of how false the depression diagnosis can be based on the symptoms studied. Additionally, bipolar elements are added that identify how effective a treatment is in the patient, considering the side effects on health. Consequently, this implicit bipolar neutrosophic value determined as \tilde{A} in each analyzed set and subset implies a representation in the following functions (according to

Definition 5):

- $f(\{\tilde{s}_n\}) \rightarrow \tilde{d}_n$
- $f(\{\tilde{d}_n\}) \rightarrow \tilde{t}_n$

Another recurring issue is the patient's age (e_n) and the gender (g_n) for example, major depressive disorder is observed as more frequent in 7% of people worldwide, primarily women. It is even three times more frequent among those aged 18 to 29 years than in those over 60 years. Therefore, these attributes should be included in the neutrosophic structure of the function:

- $f(\{\tilde{s}_n\} \cap \{e_n\} \cap \{g_n\}) \rightarrow \tilde{d}_n$
- $f(\{\tilde{d}_n\}) \rightarrow \tilde{t}_n$

Another example shows the following clinical picture, where the following function is observed in a young patient:

$$f(\{\tilde{s}_n\} \cap \{23\} \cap \{male\}) \rightarrow \text{Mild depression}$$

Where $\{\tilde{s}_n\}$ is defined within the following context: a 23-year-old young man who, despite feeling depressed, withdrawn, and with low self-esteem, could continue his work on the family farm, although he spoke very slowly and appeared somewhat distant. This case illustrates how the distress, while present, is still manageable and does not result in complete incapacitation.

In fact, the subset of $\{\tilde{s}_n\}$ allows for defining and establishing a clinical diagnosis, which in this case shows that the patient presents mild depression, characterized by a lower quantity and intensity of symptoms, generally accompanied by mild or moderate functional impairment. According to the Beck Depression Inventory-II (BDI-II), a score between 14 and 19 is considered indicative of mild depression. According to DSM-5 criteria, mild episodes may include only five or six depressive symptoms, with limited intensity, allowing the individual to partially preserve their functional capacity, although with unusual effort. These individuals experience distress but usually maintain their work or academic activity with some degree of performance.

In another analysis, of a patient, the following function has been determined:

$$f(\{\tilde{s}_n\} \cap \{18\} \cap \{female\}) \rightarrow \text{Severe depression}$$

Where $\{\tilde{s}_n\}$ manifests in the patient with intentional injury behavior through burns, indicating profound emotional dysregulation and a severe sense of hopelessness. This type of behavior reflects not only the severity of the disorder but also the urgency for specific and sustained interventions.

In fact, severe depression implies a greater number of symptoms with high intensity, and a significant functional impact that can become disabling. In the BDI-II, a score of 29 to 63 suggests a severe depressive episode. These episodes usually substantially compromise the individual's autonomy, interfering with their academic and work performance and daily life. Withdrawal behaviors, profound hopelessness, marked anhedonia, notable cognitive alterations, and in some cases, self-injurious behaviors or suicidal ideation are observed.

Therefore, it has been observed that $\{\tilde{s}_n\}$ constitutes a set formed by several subsets that interrelate from defined and partially defined structures in bipolar neutrosophic degrees. In fact, evaluating \tilde{d}_n does not depend solely on the level of symptoms presented and their degrees of complexity defined on a scale $[0,1]$, but depends on elements of opposite poles such as professional experience, patient health coverage, or similar clinical conditions defined in the range $[-1,0]$.

Similarly, \tilde{t}_n is structured in treatment subsets, which are defined in how true the success of the treatment can be, or indeterminate when compromising effectiveness due to concurrence with other pathologies. As well as the degree of falseness determined by the low or null commitment of the patient

to undergo treatment. Thus, they are defined within a range of $[0,1]$ for each evaluated parameter.

On the other hand, the level of truth about how this treatment compromises according to the expected side effects must be evaluated, or it is partially affected or indeterminate when evidence shows that a result is not as expected. As well as a degree of falseness identified in the minimization of side effects, so that these would be found in a range of $[-1,0]$. These structures, subsets, and sets are visualized in Figure 1 from the bipolar neutrosophic analysis.

Figure 1: Bipolar neutrosophic representation of depression and its treatment. Source: Own elaboration.

Case study: Once the bipolar neutrosophic representation is defined, the analysis of severe depression in young adults is developed through a case study, where it constitutes a relevant clinical and social challenge, particularly in Latin American countries where mental health infrastructure does not adequately cover the maintenance phase. Evidence indicates that the risk of relapsing after a severe depressive episode is high, even when effective treatment such as Cognitive-Behavioral Therapy (CBT) has been received.

In Ecuador, this gap becomes more evident in intermediate cities such as Ambato, where community psychological resources are limited and the stigma associated with mental health hinders continuity of care. In this context, designing a specific protocol for young people between 18 and 25 years old not only responds to a clinical need but also to an opportunity for preventive impact at a key stage of development. Therefore, the function to be analyzed in this study is represented:

:

- $f(\{\tilde{s}_n\} \cap \{\{18 - 25\} \cap \{g_n\}\}) \rightarrow \{Severe\ depression\}$
- $f(\{Severe\ depression\}) \rightarrow \{\{CBT\} \cap \{ACT\} *\}$

Where, the structure $\{\{CBT\} \cap \{ACT\} *\}$ is included in a neutrosophic area in the subset t_1 and $\{Severe\ depression\}$ as a subset of \tilde{d}_n (in fact, these patients must be in partial or total remission of the depressive episode). Therefore, the inclusion and intersection with ACT treatment according to $\{\tilde{s}_n\}$ is considered (see Table 1).

Table 1: Psychosocial risk factors $\{s_n\}$ in young people from Ambato and their relationship with protocol design.

Domain	Specific Risk Factor	Consideration in the ACT Protocol
Family	Psychiatric history, family abandonment, marital conflicts, early pregnancies.	Relevant context for values clarification and acceptance of discomfort.
Academic	Academic load, social stressors, learning difficulties, exam-related stress.	Initial assessment and guidance for defusion and mindfulness activities.
Individual	Low self-esteem, anxiety, anhedonia, lack of resilience and coping strategies.	Directly addressed through all psychological flexibility processes.
Social	Economic pressure, substance use, family expectations, bullying.	Indirect work on context and connection with personal values.
Work (young workers and health professionals)	Mobbing, stress, double burden, job insecurity.	Support for clarification of values and acceptance of work-related distress.

Next, under the conditions of the case study, an analysis is performed between the following structures $\{ACT\}, \{CBT\}$ y $\{\{CBT\}, \{ACT\}*\}$ (se define $\{ACT\}*$ is defined to be implemented in the maintenance phase) (see Tables 2 and 3). For this purpose, the following identified parameters (b_i) and weights (w_j) distributed for obtaining the score, accuracy and certainty functions were determined (calculated according to definitions 6 and 7):

- b_1 : Main approach
- b_2 : Therapeutic objective
- b_3 : Relationship with thoughts
- b_4 : Main strategies
- b_5 : Symptom reduction in young people
- b_6 : Long-term goal

Table 2: Analysis between structures belonging to subset t_1 . Source: Own elaboration.

t_1	b_1	b_2	b_3	b_4	b_5	b_6
w_j	0.16	0.18	0.16	0.16	0.18	0.16
$\{CBT\}$	(0.64,0.41,0.42, -0.72,-0.29,-0.3)	(0.74,0.31,0.32, -0.52,-0.49,-0.5)	(0.74,0.31,0.32, -0.42,-0.59,-0.6)	(0.74,0.31,0.32, -0.12,-0.89,-0.9)	(0.64,0.41,0.42, -0.02,-0.93,-0.98)	(0.64,0.41,0.42, -0.82,-0.19,-0.2)
$\{ACT\}$	(0.84,0.21,0.22, -0.12,-0.89,-0.9)	(0.64,0.41,0.42, -0.22,-0.79,-0.8)	(0.84,0.21,0.22, -0.52,-0.49,-0.5)	(0.84,0.21,0.22, -0.52,-0.49,-0.5)	(0.84,0.21,0.22, -0.02,-0.93,-0.98)	(0.84,0.21,0.22, -0.12,-0.89,-0.9)
$\{\{CBT\}, \{ACT\}*\}$	(0.94,0.11,0.12, -0.02,-0.93,-0.98)	(0.84,0.21,0.22, -0.12,-0.89,-0.9)	(0.74,0.31,0.32, -0.32,-0.69,-0.7)	(0.94,0.11,0.12, -0.32,-0.69,-0.7)	(0.84,0.21,0.22, -0.52,-0.49,-0.5)	(0.84,0.21,0.22, -0.22,-0.79,-0.8)

Table 3: Evaluation of score, accuracy and certainty functions. Source: Own elaboration.

t_1	$w_j x b_i$	$\tilde{l}(\tilde{a})$	$\tilde{a}(\tilde{a})$	$\tilde{c}(\tilde{a})$
$\{CBT\}$	(0.694,0.357,0.367,-0.251,-0.694,-0.762)	0.696	0.838	1.456
$\{ACT\}$	(0.815,0.237,0.247,-0.155,-0.814,-0.858)	0.808	1.271	1.673
$\{\{CBT\}, \{ACT\}*\}$	(0.874,0.182,0.192,-0.177,-0.792,-0.836)	0.825	1.341	1.71

It is observed that $\{\{CBT\}, \{ACT\}*\}$ obtained a score of $\tilde{l}(\tilde{a}) = 0.825$ by including ACT treatment in the maintenance phase above the others. On the other hand, given that the values of $\tilde{l}(\tilde{a})$ are different, it is not necessary to use the other functions.

Comparative analysis: Cognitive-Behavioral Therapy (CBT) is recognized as a treatment of choice for adults in the acute phase of Major Depressive Disorder (MDD) from moderate to severe, as well as for mild cases. Its recent use has been observed with CBT monotherapy, as well as its combination with antidepressants for depression treatment.

Regarding relapse prevention, available evidence indicates that CBT offers efficacy both in the short

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and long term. Thus, it shows a significant reduction in relapses or recurrences compared to pharmacological or psychological placebo treatments.

However, the studies reviewed in the bibliography of this research do not detail specific limitations of traditional CBT in preventing relapses in cases of severe depression compared to other active therapies. Although general disadvantages of the traditional CBT model are noted, such as its focus mainly on current symptoms rather than the historical origins of distress. Even its possible excessive focus on conscious thinking and the tendency to combat suffering in a way that could promote maladaptive avoidance strategies. These observations are not presented as empirically confirmed limitations in the context of severe relapse prevention.

To conclude, some criticisms directed at clinical guidelines mention that they do not incorporate all available psychological treatment options with empirical support, suggesting the existence of effective therapeutic alternatives. Although without explicitly stating that CBT presents specific deficiencies in preventing severe relapses.

In contrast, available evidence shows that Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT) offers notable advantages for working on relapse prevention, as it explicitly incorporates the goal of preventing future relapses as part of the behavioral change it seeks to promote. Unlike approaches focused solely on symptom eradication, ACT is oriented toward increasing psychological flexibility, teaching people to accept difficult thoughts, emotions, and internal experiences without fighting against them or trying to eliminate them.

Therefore, the treatment defined in the neutrosophic structure $\{\{CBT\}, \{ACT\}*\}$ seeks to promote psychological flexibility, prevent relapses, and favor sustained emotional well-being in a population of young adults between 18 and 25 years old. This bipolar neutrosophic area is delimited, as it is applicable to patients with a history of severe depression belonging to the subset of \tilde{d}_n , previously treated with CBT. In fact, the inclusion of ACT in the neutrosophic structure works to teach people to stay connected with the present moment through active acceptance of their internal experience, allowing them to advance toward their goals and vital purposes, despite emotional distress.

This approach is particularly useful for relapsing prevention, as it recognizes that distress and unwanted private events are inevitable in life. Instead of focusing on their control or avoidance, fostering rigid patterns of destructive experiential avoidance, ACT equips individuals with skills to manage these events functionally, building a life coherent with their personal values, even in the presence of emotional difficulties.

3.2 Intervention program designed or adapted defined in $\{\{CBT\}, \{ACT\}*\}$

3.2.1 General objective: The present protocol aims to design a maintenance plan based on Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT), directed at young adults between 18 and 25 years old with a history of severe depression previously treated with Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT), with the purpose of promoting psychological flexibility, preventing relapses, and favoring sustained emotional well-being.

3.2.2 Specific objectives:

- Strengthen psychological flexibility in participants through the integration of techniques based on acceptance, cognitive defusion, and committed action
- Identify personal values and promote behaviors aligned with such values as a guide for meaningful post-treatment life
- Develop mindfulness skills and contact with the present moment to improve emotional regulation and reduce experiential avoidance patterns
- Evaluate positive maintenance indicators and early detection of relapses through validated scales and qualitative interviews
- Foster functional coping strategies for internal events (thoughts, emotions) without the need to eliminate psychological distress

3.2.3 Agents involved in the implementation of the intervention program

The present protocol would be implemented by a team of mental health professionals with training in Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT), composed of clinical psychologists and therapists certified in mindfulness-based interventions and third-generation therapies. The facilitators must have experience working with young adults and prior training in group approaches, as the intervention follows a group-based, experiential, and hands-on format.

Additionally, the participation of an external clinical supervisor with knowledge in ACT is required, who is responsible for evaluating compliance with the ethical and technical standards of the protocol. This supervisor also provides weekly supervision spaces for the therapists in charge, with the purpose of maintaining therapeutic quality, addressing special cases, and preventing professional burnout. The implementation of the program is developed in coordination with educational institutions or community mental health centers in Ambato, which would provide the physical space, logistical resources, and administrative support necessary for the execution of sessions.

For the formation of intervention groups, an estimated range of six to ten participants per cohort is established. This number allows maintaining a balance between meaningful group interaction and personalized attention, favoring active participation, monitoring of individual processes, and development of experiential exercises in a contained and manageable environment. This size is also consistent with the methodological principles of ACT and the experiential nature of the sessions. The following table presents a summary of the main agents involved in the intervention, their specific roles and functions (see Table 4).

Table 4: Agents involved in protocol implementation. Source: Own elaboration.

Agent	Role	Main functions
Main therapist	Group facilitator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct group sessions. • Apply ACT techniques.
Co-therapist / assistant	Technical and clinical support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conduct clinical follow-up. • Assist in dynamics. • Record observations. • Provide individual containment.
Clinical supervisor	Therapeutic quality control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weekly supervision. • Case review. • Ethical and technical support.
Collaborating institution	Institutional and logistical support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide space. • Convene participants. • Coordinate material resources.
Participants	Protocol beneficiaries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Actively attend. • Participate in sessions. • Apply strategies between sessions.

3.2.4 Actions to be developed and didactic resources employed

The following section delves into the specific contents of each protocol session, structured around the six core processes of Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT). Each session integrates practical techniques designed to strengthen psychological flexibility and promote the maintenance of therapeutic gains achieved during the acute phase of treatment (see Table 5).

Table 5: Detailed contents by session. Source: Own elaboration.

No.	Session	Objective	Techniques	Homework
1	Introduction to the protocol and the ACT model	To provide psychoeducation on severe depression, explain the psychological flexibility model (Hexa-flex), and present the structure of the protocol.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participatory explanation of the ACT model and its six core processes. • Group activity: "Expectations and personal commitment." • Presentation of the group therapeutic contract. 	Brief diary on the most frequent thoughts and emotions during the week.
2	Accepting distress	To promote active acceptance of difficult thoughts and emotions without attempting to avoid or suppress them.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experiential exercise: "Making room" (allowing an uncomfortable emotion to be present without struggle). • Guided discussion on the consequences of experiential avoidance. • Metaphor: "The unwanted guest" (accepting the arrival of thoughts/emotions as visitors). 	Guided acceptance practice using a 10-minute audio recording.
3	Cognitive defusion	To teach strategies for observing thoughts as mental events in order to reduce their impact and control.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exercise: "Leaves on a stream" (visualizing thoughts floating on a river). • Verbal exercise: "Word repetition" (repeating a key thought until it loses its emotional charge). • Group reflection on the influence of automatic thoughts 	Apply defusion techniques at least twice daily, recording the experience in the journal.
4	Contact with the present moment	To develop mindfulness skills to enhance present-moment awareness and emotional regulation.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Formal mindfulness practice: "Mindful breathing" (10-minute guided session). • Open attention exercise: "Body scan." • Group analysis on the importance of conscious presence in relapse prevention. 	Daily mindfulness practice (audio recording provided).
5	Self-as-context	To promote the development of a flexible self-perspective that allows internal experiences to be observed without full identification.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Guided exercise: "The constant observer" (identification of the part of the self that is always present). • Metaphor: "The chessboard" (the distinction between the pieces in conflict and the board that holds them). • Activity: Sharing experiences of being "carried away" by emotions and how they could have been observed from a distance. 	Written reflection on difficult situations and the perspective of the "observing self."
6	Values clarification	To facilitate the identification of personal values and their role as a compass to guide meaningful actions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exercise: "The life wheel" (identifying key life domains and values within each). • Visualization: "The funeral" 	Define three micro-actions aligned with the identified values.

			(imagining how one would like to be remembered to detect core values).	
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Group discussion on the differences between values and goals. 	
7	Committed action	To assist participants in turning personal values into concrete and sustainable actions, even in the presence of emotional discomfort.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Behavioral planning: Development of a weekly action plan (based on values). • Barrier analysis: Identification of internal and external obstacles and strategies to overcome them. • Metaphor: "The garden" (nurturing values as if tending a garden). 	Carry out at least one committed action and record the experience.
8	Integration and relapse prevention	To integrate the learnings from the protocol and establish a personalized relapse prevention plan.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Group review of progress and key learnings. • Development of a "Personal relapse prevention map" (identifying early warning signs and coping strategies). • Symbolic closing activity: "Letter to my future self." 	Continue autonomous maintenance and follow-up practices.

3.2.5 Schedule or timeline (see Table 6)

Table 6: Weekly intervention schedule based on ACT processes. Source: Own elaboration.

Week	Session Topic	Main ACT Process	Specific Objective
1	Introduction and psychoeducation on ACT	Hexaflex Model	Understanding protocol structure
2	Acceptance of emotional distress	Acceptance	Reducing experiential avoidance
3	Cognitive defusion	Cognitive defusion	Changing relationship with thoughts
4	Mindfulness and present-moment awareness	Present-moment contact	Improving emotional regulation
5	The self as context	Self as context	Building a flexible self-perspective
6	Values clarification	Values clarification	Identifying life purpose and direction
7	Committed action	Committed action	Converting values into meaningful behavior
8	Integration and relapse prevention	Integration of ACT processes	Consolidating learning and planning prevention

3.3 Discussion

The bipolar neutrosophic analysis has facilitated the identification of attributes, structures, subsets, and sets implicit in the diagnosis and treatment of depression. By presenting bipolar characteristics, it has been observed that it is not sufficient to only consider the positive degrees of truth in sets of attributes that determine the clinical type or subtype of depression. In fact, negative degrees must be included in representation of attributes such as low professional experience, patient health coverage, or similar clinical conditions defined in the range of attributes of the presented diagnosis [11]. Therefore, the clinical subtype of depression must be identified and determined, managing existing indeterminacies and

enhancing results from protocols designed for each subset of the identified population.

On the other hand, the case study analysis regarding the neutrosophic structure $\{\{CBT\}, \{ACT\}^*\}$ in the subset of young adult patients between 18 and 25 years treated with CBT has allowed for the design of a protocol aimed at promoting psychological flexibility, preventing relapses, and favoring sustained emotional well-being. Furthermore, the inclusion of ACT in the maintenance phase constitutes a valuable tool for obtaining positive results while keeping in mind the existing clinical challenges of Ambato [12].

In fact, scientific evidence has demonstrated that Acceptance and Commitment Therapy is effective not only in reducing depressive symptoms, but especially in preventing relapses in the medium and long term [13]. This is due to its capacity to strengthen transdiagnostic processes, such as acceptance, cognitive defusion, and values clarification, which allow patients to maintain adaptive functioning even in the presence of emotional distress [14]. In contrast to CBT, where the focus is on modifying cognitive content, ACT seeks to transform the relationship with thoughts and emotions, constituting a differential advantage for the maintenance phase [15].

Furthermore, the protocol responds to the urgent need to expand therapeutic options in Ecuador, where mental health remains heavily stigmatized and there are significant barriers to access and continuity in treatment. The protocol design for young university adults or those in transition to working life addresses one of the most vulnerable populations, considering psychosocial and contextual factors identified in the literature [16].

Nevertheless, although the proposal is based on a solid theoretical and empirical framework, its real effectiveness could only be determined through its application and evaluation in clinical practice. Logistical limitations, participant adherence, and the possible need for cultural or individual adjustments must be subject to continuous monitoring. Similarly, future research could explore the integration of this protocol in digital or hybrid environments to expand its accessibility.

4. Conclusion

The bipolar neutrosophic analysis has contributed to the understanding of depression through a representation of attributes, subsets, and sets implicit in the treatment of mental disorder. From the design of two neutrosophic functions, the protocol design for a small vulnerable population of young university adults in Ambato has been represented and proposed. The results have shown a proximity of the score function of 0.825 to propose a clinical protocol based on the neutrosophic structure in the treatment of severe depression.

The present maintenance protocol, based on Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT), has constituted an innovative and necessary proposal for relapse prevention in young adults aged 18 to 25 years with a history of severe depression previously treated with Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT). From an analysis of the Ecuadorian context, particularly Ambato, the protocol has been designed to strengthen psychological flexibility while promoting committed action with personal values.

The protocol has offered a clear, progressive structure adapted to the needs of the target population, integrating experiential techniques and practical exercises aligned with the six core processes of ACT. Likewise, the combination of methods and the use of bipolar Neutrosophy in the evaluation would allow obtaining a comprehensive view of the protocol's effectiveness, both in terms of symptom reduction and transformation of underlying psychological patterns. Therefore, it has been suggested to explore in future research the adaptation of the protocol to digital or hybrid modalities, with effects of increased accessibility and reach, especially in rural or hard-to-reach areas. In fact, the integration of mobile applications, virtual platforms, and telepsychology represents a promising line of work that deserves to be developed in subsequent research.

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